

GRAPHITE NANOPATELET/EPOXY VINYL ESTER COMPOSITES

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Graphite nanoplatelets (GNP) are expected to be a better reinforcement choice to polymers than carbon nanotubes because the former has the same reinforcement efficiency in 2 directions. In the present work, as-received nanoplatelets were mixed with an epoxy vinyl ester resin to study their reinforcement efficiency. The as-received GNPs had an average thickness of 20 nm. The GNP volume content was varied from 0 to 12 %. As expected, the modulus increased with increasing GNP volume content. However, the flexural strength decreased when the GNP volume exceeded 2 %. The observed increase in the modulus was much less than expected from micromechanics predictions based on a large aspect ratio. One of the reasons for such low modulus is that the measured average aspect ratio is only about 100 whereas an optimum aspect ratio is in the range of 1000. Percolation was observed around 2.5 vol% GNP to yield an electrical conductivity of 10^{-8} S/cm. Thus, the as-received GNPs can be used to improve electrical conductivity without sacrificing strength. However, further performance improvements are possible if individual graphene sheets can be separated from the as-received GNPs.

Graphite, nano, composite, platelete, gnp

Introduction

While many graphite based nanocomposite researches are focused on graphite nano-tube, benefits of exfoliated griffin sheets might not have drawn much attention so far. Exfoliated griffin sheets are extremely high in strength and also have very high aspect ratio when properly exfoliated and also have high conductivity, and they can be produced at much lower cost than nano-tubes. In contrast to some success of thermoplastic based graphite composites (e.g. Xiao et al., 2001), results on graphite composite with thermosettings, especially with epoxy, does not seem to be too encouraging in terms of mechanical property outcomes (e.g. Schadler et al, 1998; Lau and Shi, 2002). There are arguments that high particle loadings can make the matrix brittle and impair its strength (Sandler et al, 1999).

One of the most prominent geometrical models (Zallen, 1983) suggests theoretical percolation loading for spherical particles is 16 vol. % which varies in experiments to be between 5 and 20 vol. %. Meanwhile due to its high aspect ratio, graphite platelets, fibers and nano-tubes are expected to have lower percolation loadings. Taipalus and Friedrich (1998) predicted and measured conductivity percolation threshold of 2.7% in their long carbon fiber reinforced polypropylene composites with the fiber aspect ratio of 100. In the study of carbon black dispersed epoxy composite, it was found that the percolation threshold not only depends on the particle size and fractal dimension but also on the shearing rate used to disperse the carbon black particles in the matrix (Schüeler et al, 1997).

As an ongoing development, a preliminary result on particle pretreatment and “solvent assisted particle dispersion” method was introduced and promising preliminary result was presented in this paper.

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Experimental

The exfoliated graphite nanoplatelets (GNP), with SEM image as in Fig. 1., are provided by the courtesy of cornerstone inc. in Pennsylvania. Their average widths are about 1.8 μm for natural GNP and 1.6 μm /6 μm (bimodal distribution) for synthetic GNP with the aspect ratio of at least 100 or higher.

Among two types of particles, natural GNP is considered to be finer and more exfoliated. Derakane Momentum 411-350 from Dow chemical is used as a matrix which is the mixture of epoxy, vinyl ester resins and styrene whose typical structure is depicted in Fig 2. 100mL of Derakane Momentum 411-350 was used as a baseline resin amount and volume percentages of GNP was calculated as needed, and was converted to weight using the graphite density of 2 g/cm³. Then, the weighed GNP was added into the resin and manually mixed with a stirring rod for 5 minutes. Afterward, the sample was sonicated for one hour at 24 watt and 15 KHz with magnetic stirring in the mixture, and the temperature was kept around 50 °C by flowing cooling water around the reactor to prevent thermal curing of the mixture in an apparatus as schematized in Fig 3. After sonication, the mixture was vacuumed for one hour at 25 in Hg inside a vacuum chamber. The resin viscosity was measured after vacuuming using Haake viscometer. The data was recorded at a temperature of 25°C \pm 0.25°C. Then, the mixture was cured using 2 wt% of Trigonox and 0.3wt% of 6% Cobalt Nap all. After curing for more than 7 hours at room temperature, samples were postcured for an hour at 85°C. Three point bending test was performed to measure Young's modulus and flexural strength of samples with Instron machine following specifications described in ASTM D-790 (2000). 2-terminal DC measurement was used to measure electrical volume resistivity/conductivity of the samples following Cabot Test Method E043A.

(a) typical epoxy structure.

(b) typical vinyl ester structure.

Fig. 2. Typical chemical structures of matrix resins.

Fig. 3. Experimental apparatus.

Results and discussion

Fig. 4. shows plastic viscosity of uncured GNP-resin mixture fitted to Bingham model with different particle loadings. The viscosity of the mixture does not go up substantially up until 6 vol. % which is unusual compared with other nano particle systems we've dealt with such as alumina and silicon carbide whose 4% mixture has high enough viscosity to render difficulty in processing. Due to manageable viscosity of GNP-resin system, we could process composites with GNP loading of as high as 12%.

Fig. 4. Viscosity of uncured GNP-Derakane momentum 411-350 mixture.

Fig. 5. shows Young's modulus of composites with various particle loadings in relative to neat Derakane Momentum 411-350 resin whose value is measured to be 3.09 GPa. Both natural GNP and synthetic GNP composites show steady increase in modulus with increased GNP loading.

Fig. 6. shows flexural strength of composites with various particle loadings in relative to neat Derakane Momentum 411-350 resin whose value is measured to be 112 MPa. The maximum strength was observed with 2% synthetic GNP composites, and as a whole, composites with synthetic GNP

Fig. 5. Relative Young's modulus of GNP-Derakane momentum 411-350 composite

Fig. 6. Relative flexural strength of GNP-Derakane momentum 411-350 composite

showed higher strength than that with natural GNP. The material fracture usually starts at defects first. Considering other conditions are identical, more particle loading would render higher chance of particle agglomeration and clumping and this could be a source of defect and can lead to lower mechanical strengths. With 2 vol. % synthetic GNP loading rendering maximum strength, it is postulated that with current dispersion method, 2% is the optimal dispersion loading in terms of mechanical strength below which composite benefits from high strength high aspect ratio GNP and above which composite loses its strength by increased defect due to increased particle agglomeration. The finer natural GNP would have lower optimal dispersion loading with bigger number of particles per unit mass of particles. The Fig. 6. seems to support this trend.

Fig. 7. shows DC. electrical conductivity of samples with different GNP loadings. The percolation threshold value of 2.5% was observed. By putting together with the mechanical strength data in Fig. 6. the percolation threshold is low enough not to compromise the composite strength.

Even distribution of particles throughout the matrix is a critical issue to ensure defectless mechanically strengthened composite as well as lower percolation threshold.

Fig. 7. Electrical conductivity of GNP-Derakane 411-350 composite

Particle pretreatment and solvent aided dispersion:

In the experiment, it was also observed that sonication directly on resin could face some problems in processing. Fig. 8 shows change in resin color with epoxy sonication. Also, premature partial curing in vinyl ester resin sonication was observed which entails difficulty in heat dissipation. Some researchers (Sandler et al, 1999) have used ethanol to disperse carbon nanotube with sonication before adding them into epoxy. In our study, as an additional effort to enhance particle mixing and prevent above problems on resin, particle pretreatment and “solvent aided dispersion” method was employed together with a compatibility study among particle, solvent and resin systems.

Fig. 8. Apparent effect of sonication on epoxy (Epon 862) resin.

The as received Cornerstone synthetic graphite was further exfoliated by a potassium intercalation method by Dr. Kaner’s research group in UCLA (Ding et al, 2001) as in Fig 9. Graphite platelets were also manually ground with pestle and mortar as well as being acidified by sulfuric acid.

Among various solvent candidates, Isopropyl alcohol was found to be very compatible with graphite and held the graphite suspension quite stable as in Fig. 10., and also was readily miscible with epoxy, vinylester and styrene. By practicing sonication in solvent environment, the particle dispersion in solvent can be achieved without limitation on sonication intensity. By mixing them into compatible resin system mechanically, the well dispersed particle suspension in solvent can be maintained in the resin matrix until the solvents are evaporated and composites are cured.

Fig. 9. Partially exfoliated graphite platelets.

The variables are rather collectively oriented for this purpose. The effect of individual variables, with systematic design of experiment, will be a subject of future experiments.

This experiment was focused on rapid production of data showing improved mechanical properties based on well reasoned out intuition rather than being analytically designed to see effects of individual process variables on final properties. The

Fig. 10. Various solvent – graphite suspensions 5 mins. after initial 1 min. co-shaking of

Fig. 11. compares Young’s modulus of 1 vol. % gnp-epoxy composites between pestle ground / acidified graphite and unground / untreated graphite prepared by the solvent aided dispersion method. The result shows that the graphite grinding and acid treatment collectively helps to improve modulus of the composites. Fig. 11. also shows that the sample taken from the top shows higher modulus than those taken from the bottom, strongly suggesting sedimentation during the curing process.

Fig. 11. Flexural modulus of 1% gnp-epon862 composites prepared by solvent aided particle dispersion method. (a) gnp treated with sulfuric acid and ground with pestle & mortar (b) gnp not treated and not ground.

Fig. 12. compares flexural strength of 1 vol. % gnp-epoxy composites among pestle ground / acidified graphite and unground / untreated graphite prepared by the solvent aided dispersion method; and also samples prepared by direct particle / resin mixing and sonication method. The comparison shows that the use of solvent aided particle dispersion method produced stronger samples than those prepared by direct particle/resin mixing and direct sonication on resin. The result also shows that the graphite grinding and acid treatment collectively helps to improve strength of the composites. Fig. 12. also shows that the sample taken from the top shows higher modulus than those taken from the bottom, strongly suggesting sedimentation during the curing process.

Fig. 12. Flexural strength of 1% gnp-epon862 composites (a) gnp treated with sulfuric acid and ground with pestle & mortar (b) gnp not treated and not ground prepared by solvent aided particle dispersion method, (c) gnp not treated and not ground prepared by direct particle / resin mixing and sonication method.

Fig. 13. compares Young's modulus of 1 vol. % gnp-derakane411-355 composites between pestle ground / acidified graphite and unground / untreated graphite prepared by the solvent aided dispersion method. As in the case with epon862 composite, result shows that the graphite grinding and acid treatment collectively helps to improve modulus of the composite. Particle sedimentation effect is not as pronouncing as in the epoxy composite case. This can be attributed to the difference in the curing process of the two resin systems. Epon 862 is cured at high temperature and during its high temperature period, mixture viscosity is kept very low for an extended period time (more than 1 hr. @ 125 °C) before curing initiates hence allowing particle sedimentation, while Derakane composite undergoes rapid room temperature curing rendering unfavorable environment for sedimentation.

Fig. 14. compares flexural strength of 1 vol. % gnp-derakane411-355 composites between pestle ground / acidified graphite and unground / untreated graphite prepared by the solvent aided dispersion method; and also samples prepared by direct particle / resin mixing and sonication method. As in the case with epon862 composite, result shows that the graphite grinding and acid treatment collectively helps to improve strength of the composite. Samples taken at the bottom clearly follows the epoxy composite case, however, samples taken at the top do not show the trend. More consistent trend is that the ground graphite sample shows minimal sedimentation compared with unground graphite sample.

Fig. 13. Flexural modulus of 1% gnp-derakane411-355 composites prepared by solvent aided particle dispersion method. (a) gnp treated with sulfuric acid and ground with pestle & mortar (b) gnp not treated and not ground.

Fig. 14. Flexural strength of 1% gnp-derakane411-355 composites (a) gnp treated with sulfuric acid and ground with pestle & mortar (b) gnp not treated and not ground, prepared by solvent aided particle dispersion method, (c) gnp not treated and not ground prepared by direct particle / resin mixing and sonication method.

Conclusions

Using the method of combined sonication and magnetic stirring, epoxy vinyl ester – based composites were produced using exfoliated graphite nano-platelets. The composite thus prepared showed maximum flexural strength at 2 vol. % synthetic GNP loading and showed percolation threshold at 2.5 vol. %.

Grinding and treatment of GNP with sulfuric acid together with the solvent aided dispersion helps to improve mechanical properties of the composite. Particle sedimentation is also minimized by particle grinding and acid treatment.

With the glimpse of possible property improvement with particle grinding, acid treatment, and solvent aided dispersion, it is desired to do more systematic well designed experiment to evaluate the contribution of each variable on final properties of the composite. Additionally, as suggested by some researches (Sandler et al., 1999), using high shear mixing is expected to lower electrical percolation threshold loading of the graphite in the composite as well as improving mechanical properties of the composite due to better mixing and formation of nanographite network.

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